

GEOPOLITICA

RIVISTA DI POLITICA INTERNAZIONALE

JOURNAL OF GEOPOLITICS AND RELATED MATTERS

CONFINE E FRONTIERA

GEOPOLITICA, DIRITTO E RELAZIONI INTERNAZIONALI

BORDER AND FRONTIER

GEOPOLITICS, INTERNATIONAL LAW AND RELATIONS

I concetti di confine e frontiera sono stati centrali nella teoria geopolitica, nel diritto internazionale e nello studio delle relazioni internazionali. Questo numero di GEOPOLITICA - curato da Federico Bordonaro e Tiberio Graziani - si propone di esplorare le molteplici dimensioni di tali concetti, tracciandone l'evoluzione storica ed esaminando la loro rilevanza e trasformazione nella ricerca accademica contemporanea e nelle applicazioni pratiche.

Questo numero di GEOPOLITICA gode del patrocinio di:

Società Italiana di Geopolitica - progetto di Vision & Global Trends

The concepts of border and frontier have been central to geopolitical theory, international law, and the study of international relations. This issue of GEOPOLITICA - edited by Federico Bordonaro and Tiberio Graziani - aims to explore the multiple dimensions of these concepts, tracing their historical evolution and examining their relevance and transformation in contemporary academic research and practical applications.

This issue of GEOPOLITICA is published under the patronage of Società Italiana di Geopolitica - a project by Vision & Global Trends

GEOPOLITICA Vol. XIV N. 1/2025 Gennaio - Giugno / January - June

ISSN 2009-9193

<https://www.geopoliticarivista.it/>

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GEOPOLITICA

CONFINE E FRONTIERA

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JOURNAL OF GEOPOLITICS AND RELATED MATTERS

ISSN 2009-9193 - Vol. XIV - n. 1/2025 GENNAIO-GIUGNO / JANUARY-JUNE

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a cura di / edited by: Federico Bordonaro & Tiberio Graziani. Autori/Authors: Ferdinando Angeletti, Giuseppe Anzera, Alberto Catania, Isabella M. Chiara, Manuela Cicerchia, Paolo Cornetti, Alberto Cossu, Marco Dordoni, Giacinto D'Urso, Mark L. Entin, Ekaterina G. Entina, Mario Gennatiempo, Alfonso Giordano, Giorgio Giosafatto, Said S. Gulyamov, Phil Kelly, Andrea Komlosy, Gino Lanzara, Giuliano Luongo, Alessandra Massa, Carole Massalsky, Zaem Hassan Mehmood, Fabio Mini, Gianluca Pastori, Giuseppe Romeo, Francesco Valacchi, Lucas De Arruda Zani

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Autori/Authors

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GEOPOLITICA

Direzione

Piazza dei Navigatori, 22 – 00147 – Roma – Italia
T. +39 334 111 70 81
tibgraziani@gmail.com
<https://www.geopoliticarivista.it/>

CALLIVE EDIZIONI

whatsapp +39 339 495 41 75 - callive.srls@gmail.com
Direttore editoriale: Santo Strati
in collaborazione con Media&Books

ISBN: 9791281485211

Geopolitica – Registrazione presso il Tribunale di Roma
in data 21 dicembre 2011, n. 395/2011
Direttore responsabile: Tiberio Graziani

GEOPOLITICA

DIRETTORE: TIBERIO GRAZIANI

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La rivista aderisce alle linee guida adottate dal Committee on the Publication Ethics (<http://publicationethics.org/resources/guidelines>) a cui fa rinvio il Regolamento dell'ANVUR per la classificazione delle riviste nelle aree non bibliometriche.

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The role of emerging maritime technologies in redefining geopolitical frontiers in the Indo-Pacific

Zaeem Hassan Mehmood¹

Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan

ABSTRACT

In the Indo-Pacific, emerging maritime technologies are reshaping geopolitical dynamics by challenging traditional notions of borders and sovereignty at sea. Traditionally, borders have been viewed as fixed territorial lines, but the high seas represent a contested and fluid space that challenge traditional notions of sovereignty and state authority. The paper explores the impact of advanced technologies such as autonomous vessels, maritime surveillance systems, artificial intelligence and undersea infrastructure in redefining maritime boundaries and geopolitical frontiers. These maritime technologies have further enhanced existing mapping capabilities and resource assessment allowing states to exploit and secure their maritime frontiers. It examines how these developments challenge existing ocean governance regimes and maritime law. The paper uses a qualitative approach to analyze maritime legal frameworks and case studies of contested regions within the Indo-Pacific, such as the Indian Ocean and the South China Sea. It offers valuable insights on how technological advancements transform regional maritime frontiers based on interviews with maritime law experts and discussions with policymakers. These perspectives highlight how the increasing role of technology extends state influence, reshapes legal interpretations of maritime boundaries and raises questions about the adequacy of current international legal regimes. The study contributes to understanding the role of maritime technology, its potential to alter power dynamics in the Indo-Pacific, and its implications for future ocean governance regime.

KEYWORDS: Emerging Maritime Technologies, Autonomous Vessels, Artificial Intelligence, Maritime Security, Indo-Pacific, Indian Ocean, South China Sea

¹ The author is PhD scholar at Greenwich University, Karachi. He has a Master's of Philosophy in Strategic Studies specializing in maritime security from National Defence University, Islamabad. He is an alumnus of 2024 Deep Dive Programme of International Seabed Authority on United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea.

Introduction

The Indo-Pacific is a region characterized by global power competition due to its economic significance, critical maritime trade routes and contested geopolitical frontiers (Rondeau, 2023). In the maritime realm, the oceanic boundaries were traditionally conceived as fixed territorial demarcations governed by the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), considered the ‘constitution of the ocean’ (McKinley, 2024). However, since then several developments have taken place as a result of advanced maritime technologies that have provided states new ways to project their power and assert control over oceanic resources. These emerging technologies² include autonomous ships, artificial intelligence, improved maritime surveying systems and undersea infrastructure. These innovations have made it possible to monitor, navigate and exploit the ocean in unprecedented ways, extending state control into previously unreachable areas (Agarwala, 2022).

As a result of high-resolution mapping and unmanned deep-sea exploration technologies it has become relatively cost-effective to extract resources from the sea (Santos et al., 2018). Additionally, unmanned and autonomous maritime systems enable better surveillance and control of maritime frontiers. Surveys have indicated significant reserves of living and non-living resources, particularly critical minerals like cobalt, nickel, and manganese, essential for the global green transition to low-carbon and zero-carbon technologies, including electric vehicles have been discovered (Cassotta & Goodsite, 2023). Due to their abundance in key Indo-Pacific sub-regions such as the Indian Ocean and South China Sea, rich in these resources, would further intensify as their centrality as hotspots for technological investment and strategic competition.

The paper explores the transformative impact of these technologies on the geopolitical landscape of the Indo-Pacific. The study adopts a

² Emerging technologies refers to cutting-edge innovations that are in the process of development or early adoption, with the potential to significantly transform industries and societies. While all technology evolves continuously, the term highlights those breakthroughs that represent paradigm shifts in capabilities, applications, and implications. These technologies often have dual-use potential, meaning they can serve both civilian and military purposes. They comprise of: artificial intelligence, autonomous systems, and satellite imaging.

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qualitative methodology, combining analysis with case studies and expert interviews, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implications of technological advancement on ocean frontiers.

Geopolitics of the Ocean Frontiers

The oceans have emerged as a major focus of global geopolitics in the 21st century (Gray, Acton, Campbell, 2024). They are at the center of numerous new and renewed efforts by states to assert sovereignty and secure economic opportunities. The ocean frontiers differ fundamentally from terrestrial systems due to their fluidity and dynamism. Unlike borders, which act as fixed lines of division, frontiers are zones of contested sovereignty and influence (Kristof, 1959). This distinction is evident in the historical evolution of maritime strategies. Admiral Philip Colomb described Britain's frontier as the enemy's coast (Colomb, 1895), emphasizing the projection of power across the entire maritime frontier. Today, advanced maritime technologies enable states to monitor and control these spaces continuously, even in peacetime, where oceans increasingly belong to the strongest powers (Castex, 1994; Berkowitz, 2014).

Maritime scholars have developed various approaches for studying the oceans as frontiers in the borderless world of globalization. Braverman and Johnson (2020: 10-14) describe how UNCLOS has mapped the ocean into multiple zones and jurisdictions that corresponds to a land-based Westphalian concept of nation-state sovereignty. However, contrary to the Westphalian terrestrial thinking of a map-like view of the oceans, the materiality of the ocean waters suggests that maritime frontiers are more than fixed lines across the sea surface. Peters (2020: 45) elaborates this further by stating that "the sea has a three-dimensional depth; it has a material form a liquid; and is in constant motion." By using a volumetric approach to describe the ocean geopolitics based on this ocean dynamics and materiality, Steinberg and Peters (2015) advance the idea of "wet ontology".

Havice and Zalik (2018), describe the oceans as a 'commodity frontier' providing untapped living and non-living mineral resources, while is increasingly becoming a scientific and jurisdictional frontier. Rasmus-

sen and Lund (2018) call the oceans as a “resource frontier,” possessing new resources some of which are yet to be discovered and extracted. Steinberg (2018: 237-240) argues that a frontier is “a zone of declining power and is less a line” as opposed to “a border that is a division line between two equivalent entities.” For Steinberg the distinction between borders and frontiers is seen as a dynamic process and that when frontiers are territorialized, “existing institutional orders can be disrupted, redefined or reinterpreted and new institutional and rights regimes accompanying the struggles for legitimizing the process are often set in motion.” (Havice and Zalik, 2019: 221). Therefore based on the assessment of Steinberg (2018: 240), the closing of the frontiers, opens up new frontiers, creating a cycle of opportunity that is triggered by the new frontier.

Tazzioli (2018) deliberates on “mobile border” as a concept that provides “mobile sovereignty.” Everuss (2020: 1-5) furthers this idea and explains how it can be extended over the ocean frontiers with the development of autonomous unmanned systems, floating islands and advanced maritime technologies that expand state sovereignty while making the oceans more transparent in the coming decades (Mehmood, 2024). In the South China Sea, states use the oceanic space as ‘mobile state powers’ in various ways to exercise territorial control (Guilfoyle, 2019; Mawyer, 2021). Hung and Liens argue that “weaponization of fishing fleets” by China is an attempt to assert its territorial claims and in this case study fishing vessels serve as “mobile infrastructure” for exercising state sovereignty over contested maritime frontiers (Kennedy, 2018; Patalano, 2018).

Harold (2017) provides the concept of “maritime gray zone” to elaborate the complexity of sovereignty, territory and ocean frontiers in regions such as the Indo-Pacific. Maritime gray zone refers to a competitive situation between peace and armed conflict that involves tactics calculated to advance border disputes while avoiding direct armed conflict (Lee, 2020). In the South China Sea, China’s alleged weaponization of fishing fleets to assert territorial claims transforms these vessels into mobile floating instruments of state sovereignty (Kennedy, 2018; Patalano, 2018). Moreover, the reclamation and island-building activities by states in the

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Indo-Pacific to assert territorial claims exemplify the securitization of maritime spaces (Davenport, 2018).

This securitization of the maritime domain intersects with broader geopolitical trends in the Indo-Pacific, where technological advancements redefine the region's oceanic frontiers. The race to incorporate, control and deny access to emerging innovations in maritime technologies underscores the intensifying competition among states. From an international relations lens, this competition mirrors Machiavellian realism, where power dynamics increasingly depend on assuming strategic control of key oceanic frontiers and denying the same to adversaries (Gardner, 2006; Cropsey, 2020).

Furthermore, the oceans often described as anarchical spaces, characterize a Hobbesian state of nature where the absence of a central authority leads to a system dictated by self-interest and competition (Crow, 2020). In this context, states are impelled to take unilateral actions to safeguard their interests, preserve and extend their sovereignty, and establish control over key oceanic frontiers. Since international frameworks like UNCLOS lack the means to enforce governance structures, particularly when great powers have competing interests, oceanic interactions would be shaped by principles such as might makes it right. As a result, anarchic oceans environment, coupled with militarization and deployment of advanced maritime technologies, challenges the notion of the ocean as the common heritage of mankind. Consequently, these developments reinforce the realist paradigm, with states prioritizing survival, security and dominance, reshaping maritime norms and cooperative frameworks in favor of unilateral gains.

The interplay of sovereignty, technology and competition in the Indo-Pacific echoes the broader geopolitics of ocean frontiers. Similar dynamics are developing in other maritime regions, such as the Arctic, where states are attempting to contest sovereignty over the resource-rich frontiers as a result of melting sea ice (Auerswald, 2020). In the Indian Ocean, it is the geopolitics of mining in the deep sea that highlights interplay between resource accumulation, state control of key ocean spaces and environmental concerns (Hallgren & Hansson, 2021). To address these concerns, states in the Global South are embracing the paradigm

of 'blue economy' which prioritizes the sustainable development of oceanic resources as a pathway to economic growth and environmental conservation (Mehmood, 2021).

Digitization of the Oceans

The digitization of the oceans transforms their security, governance, and strategic dynamics. These trends are enhanced by advancements in maritime technologies including satellite surveillance, autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), artificial intelligence (AI), and big data analytics that allow for high-resolution imagery, precise seabed mapping, and real-time surveillance (Chen et al., 2023). Since advanced technologies enable states to monitor activities across vast maritime expanses, they have both civil and military applications ranging from surface shipping to submarine operations (Kraska, 2022; Bae & Hong, 2023).

Presently, only about 20 percent of the ocean floor is mapped at high resolution, leaving vast areas uncharted (Zalik, 2018). Astonishingly, humanity knows more about the surface of the moon and planet Mars than about the depths of the oceans (Chatterjee, 2023). To address these knowledge gaps, initiatives such as the Nippon Foundation GEBCO Seabed 2030 Project has been undertaken (Mayer, 2024). For these efforts, technologies such as AI driven analytics and satellite based synthetic aperture radar are required by states to improve their capacities of monitoring oceanic activities.

However, the benefits of these developments have been distributed unevenly, between the developed and developing nations in important regions such as the Indo-Pacific. In order to increase their influence, project their power and safeguard their national interest at the ocean frontiers, developed countries such as US, China and Japan have made significant investments in state-of-the-art technologies for ocean exploration and surveillance (Lin & Yang, 2020). In contrast, many developing states of the region lack the financial resources, technological expertise and basic infrastructure necessary to enforce maritime laws and secure oceanic resources. This technological gap underlines global inequities and risks intensifying geopolitical tensions, as great powers such as US and China recognizing strategic importance of the developing states, are actively

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courting them, seeking to integrate them into their spheres of influence (Rodd, 2020; Ping, 2024). China under Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and its Maritime Silk Road, offers investments in ports, digital infrastructure and maritime technology to secure Beijing's foothold in the region (Sayed, Chowdhury & Saharuddin, 2023). The US under the framework of QUAD and Indo-Pacific Economic Framework provides capacity-building initiatives, maritime domain awareness and infrastructure development to counterbalance China's growing influence (Pham, 2024).

The Indo-Pacific: Case Study of Indian Ocean and South China Sea

The Indo-Pacific, as a geopolitical concept, has received increasing attention from policymakers in recent years. Contrary to the popular belief that the Indo-Pacific is a contemporary framework designed to counter the hegemonic rise of China, the term was originated by a German geopolitical scholar Karl Haushofer (1869–1946). Haushofer first used the “Indo-Pacific” in the 1920s, positioning it as a confluence of two great oceans, the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean. This historical origin signifies that the Indo-Pacific concept is neither exclusively American nor Indian in nature (Mehmood, 2024).

The Indo-Pacific discourse associated with strategic counterbalancing against China, oversimplifies its historical origin and essence. The idea that the Indo-Pacific framework primarily elevates India as a «net security provider» in the region is not entirely inclusive. India's strategic location and naval capabilities are significant; however the Indian Ocean's nomenclature derived from the River Indus signifies a broader regional identity (Ahsan, 2005; Vink, 2007). Moreover, the Indian Ocean basin encompasses states like Indonesia, which have the potential to play equally vital roles. Indonesia's strategic position at the crossroads of the Indian and Pacific Oceans underscores its importance in shaping the Indo-Pacific's maritime dynamics (Scott, 2019; Anwar, 2020; Mehmood, 2021). The region's importance lies in its vast expanse, which bridges diverse cultures, economies, and ecosystems, serving as a critical nexus of global maritime trade and geopolitical interactions. The strategic value of the Indo-Pacific stems from its geographical characteristics and the roles of the states within it.

The Indo-Pacific region is more than a geographical construct; it is a dynamic space shaped by intersecting geopolitical interests, security challenges, and economic imperatives (Hakata & Cannon, 2022). The growing emphasis on the Indo-Pacific reflects its centrality to global power shifts, maritime security, and economic interdependence (He, 2018; Li, 2022). The emergence and applications of new maritime technologies in the region such as autonomous vessels, underwater drones, and advanced surveillance systems has further redefined the geopolitical landscape of the Indo-Pacific.

Since Indo-Pacific's geopolitical scenario is marked by overlapping interests and competing narratives. Key regional players, including the United States, China, India, Japan, and Australia, view the Indo-Pacific through their strategic lenses (Medcalf, 2019). The United States' Free and Open Indo-Pacific (FOIP) strategy, for instance, seeks to promote a rules-based order and counter unilateral actions in contested waters. Meanwhile, China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and its maritime extensions have raised allegedly concerns about debt diplomacy and strategic encirclement. Beijing has also proposed Global Security Initiative (GSI) to reshape the security architecture by promoting an alternative to US led alliances while emphasizing mutual respect for sovereignty and non-interference (Li, 2020).

The interplay between these initiatives reflects the struggle for influence and the shaping of regional security architecture. Smaller states in the Indo-Pacific, while wary of being drawn into great power rivalries strive to maintain their strategic autonomy (Ali, 2017; Thi, 2023). Their perspectives highlight the need for inclusivity and multilateral cooperation in addressing shared challenges, such as piracy, illegal fishing, and climate change-induced maritime vulnerabilities.

Indian Ocean

The Indian Ocean has been called the “heart of the maritime world” for its geostrategic and geoeconomic significance (Mehmood 2021; Barah, 2022). It is the lifeline of global sea-based trade, stretching over 70 million square kilometers and encircles by the continents of Asia, Africa and Oceania. The Indian Ocean, home to around 2.7 billion people across 38 nations, also

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hosts vital chokepoints of the Malacca Strait, Bab-el-Mandeb and the Strait of Hormuz (Mehmood, 2022). It serves as a conduit for around 80 percent of world's maritime oil trade, as a result, its Sea Lines of Communication (SLOCs) are critical for global economy, particularly for energy dependent nations such as China, Japan and India (Bateman, 2021).

In recent years, emerging maritime technologies such as autonomous systems and unmanned platforms are being employed to project power and reassert influence in key Indian Ocean regions by both great powers and regional actors. The US and its allies to 'contain China's expanding influence,' are reported to increasingly rely on AI based surveillance structures, AUVs and sophisticated satellite networks to secure control over SLOCs and related critical maritime infrastructure (Ghaderi, 2019; Evans, 2021, Sial & Ghaffar, 2021). China has incorporated state-of-the-art technologies to bolster its naval capabilities, secure supply networks and strengthen its position by partnering with regional states to modernize ports like Gwadar and Hambantota (Smith, 2017; Bekkers et al., 2019).

In the Indian Ocean, the deep seabed, previously an unexplored frontier due to human and technological limitations with emerging maritime technologies is becoming a critical area of competition (Agarwala, 2019; Wölfl et al., 2019). Advances in unmanned underwater drones and advanced submersibles, including improved endurance batteries and pressure-resistant designs allow states to navigate and exploit the depths of the ocean, unlocking vast mineral resources. China has developed advanced deep-sea exploration capabilities in the Indian Ocean. In 2011, the International Seabed Authority (ISA) granted China a 15 year contract to explore a 10,000 square kilometer area in the Indian Ocean for polymetallic sulphides (Mehmood, 2023).

According to media reports and analysis, the area has precious metals like copper, zinc, and gold (Siddiquie, Guhar, Hashimi & Valsangkar, 1984; Roonwal, 2017). Furthermore, Beijing's exploration activities are largely possible as a result of its fleet of advanced submersibles. China holds of global record of conducting world's deepest sea dive in a manned submersible, *Fendouzhe* reached a depth of 10,909 meters in the Mariana Trench (Mehmood, 2023). As a result, its submersibles have been able

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to locate precious metals in hydrothermal sulfide deposits, which can be vital for defence industries. According to the List of North Atlantic Treaty Organization Top Critical Minerals 2024, several critical raw materials such as cobalt, manganese and rare earth elements like neodymium and samarium are sourced from the seabed (NATO, 2024).

Supply risk for critical raw materials in military applications

Source: Strategic raw materials for defence Mapping European industry needs
Benedetta Girardi, Irina Patrahau, Giovanni Cisco and Michel Rademaker
The Hague Center for Strategic Studies, January 2023

Other states in the region, such as Iran are developing emerging technologies in the military domain, as a means to asymmetrically counterbalance the might of the US. Iran has effectively deployed drones and unmanned surface vessels to monitor and at times interrupt the operations of the US Navy and its allies. Iran has developed a new drone carrier, *Shahid Bagheri* that is undergoing sea-trials (TWZ, 2024). Earlier in December 2011, it captured a US RQ-170 Sentinel unmanned aerial vehicle near Iranian city of Kashmar. More recently, in October 2023, an Iranian Army drone was able to monitor a US warship in the Indian Ocean for a reported 24 hours, underscoring Iran's continued attempts to asymmetrically challenge superior naval power of the US (Philips, 2023). In Yemen, the Houthi's use of maritime technologies

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including weapon carrying drones and unmanned platforms to disrupt shipping lanes in the Red Sea and other parts of the Western Indian Ocean is another example. These emerging technologies have allowed Houthi's to project power and carry out attacks well beyond Yemen's boundaries (Himes, 2011). Since April 2024, the Houthis have claimed responsibility for attacks on multiple vessels linked to US and Israel, including the *MSC Orion* container ship. Such incidents serve as an example of how state and non-state players in the Indian Ocean use emerging technologies to challenge great powers, disrupt maritime trade and further their geopolitical objectives. The strategic implications of these developments have significant geopolitical ramifications and they reflect broader trends of militarization and technological competition in the Indian Ocean (Bueger & Stockbruegger, 2022).

It is important to stress that the Indian Ocean is the most nuclearized ocean of the world and that regions security dynamics are increasingly complex (Mehmood, 2024). The deployment of nuclear-powered submarines by the US, China and India bring elements of deterrence and nuclear escalation into play which can be complicated with the presence of emerging maritime technologies and AI based control systems. Furthermore, the integration of emerging technologies into maritime platforms would increase the potential for miscalculation and conflict, naval standoffs and incidents. This securitization of maritime technology stresses the significance of the Indian Ocean from geopolitical and geoeconomic perspective in the great power competition unfolding in the Indo-Pacific.

South China Sea

The construction of artificial islands in the South China Sea and the use of maritime surveillance technologies by China, challenges the sovereignty claims of the neighboring states (Davenport, 2019). These include advanced radar systems, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and Unmanned Surface Vessels (USVs) and missile platforms stationed on islands, increasingly deployed to project power, assert dominance and redefine geopolitical frontiers. Lee suggests that these tactics allow Beijing to have de facto control over disputed areas challenging sovereignty claims

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of Philippines and Vietnam. Globally, South China Sea is of interest to regional and extra-regional powers, with its SLOCs carrying one-third of international maritime trade, and surveys indicating untapped energy resources (Quy, 2019). As a result, the South China Sea becomes one of the most contested maritime regions and a flashpoint in great power competition where emerging maritime technologies are tested and deployed for military-oriented missions (Dugdale, 1997; Taylor, 2014) .

A recent example of how maritime technology is being used to further geopolitical interest can be indicated by the Philippine Navy's seizing a Chinese underwater drone that was reportedly preying in their maritime borders to reconnaissance and gather intelligence (Times, 2024). This discovery and earlier reported incidents of Chinese maritime forces positioning unmarked vessels in key strategic areas in the South China Sea, also highlights the covert use of maritime technologies as a means to monitor and exert control over contested waters. These actions, illustrate the concept of 'maritime grey zones' that blurs and disguise traces of attribution to a particular state by means such as using false flag and turning off Satellite Automatic Identification System (S-AIS) to disable tracking of vessel (Parlov & Sverdup, 2024).

The use of these tactics for 'plausible deniability,' allows stronger states to extend their reach by challenging the maritime sovereignty of weaker states, while evading accountability given the complexities involved in proving intent and ownership in 'maritime grey zone operations'. The asymmetry in technological capabilities in the South China Sea intensifies regional tensions (Meng, 2017). Advanced states, have a considerable advantage over states that have not even mapped their territorial waters and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). For example, relative smaller Southeast Asian nations like Vietnam and Philippines struggle with inadequate monitoring and enforcement capabilities whereas China has access to sophisticated AUVs and a robust satellite network to enforce its extensive maritime claims. This discrepancy results in weaker states being vulnerable to maritime border intrusion and unable to respond to activities by more advanced states of activities such as illegal exploitation of living and non-living oceanic resources. Therefore, developing nations with restricted financial and technical resources regularly depend upon

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external partnerships to enhance their maritime capabilities. However, these can come with “strings attached” where foreign aid and capacity building programs are more aligned to suit strategic objectives of the donor states (Davenport, 2005).

In the South China Sea, a sub-region of the Indo-Pacific, the integration of AUVs, underwater surveillance system and emerging AI-driven platforms continue to transform maritime strategy and ocean politics. China’s “Blue Ocean Information Network” is in the developmental phase that is likely to further solidify control over disputed waters. It uses a network of satellites, unmanned platforms and AI-based smart sensors to strengthen China’s maritime claims (Asia Maritime Transparency Initiative, 2020). Similarly, US and Japan have also enhanced their maritime capabilities. The US deploys advanced underwater drones, such as *Ghost Shark* and *Orca*, designed for counter-intelligence and surveillance operations, which can operate independently and at great ocean depths for reasonable long periods (Bergmann, 2023). Japan strengthens its maritime security by integrating unmanned underwater drones with existing naval and air platforms in response to China’s increasing military presence. Additionally, Tokyo has delivered advanced radar systems to the Philippines to augment its limited capacities of monitoring the South China Sea (Castro, 2023). These developments underscore the strategic importance of the region and crucial role of emerging technologies in contemporary maritime security.

Conclusion: Way Forward

The future geographies of the ocean frontiers in the Indo-Pacific will continue to be shaped by advancements in maritime technology and regional geopolitical developments. The increasing digitization of the oceans as a result of emerging technologies in satellite imaging and autonomous systems will allow previously opaque maritime zones to become more visible, and perhaps fully transparent in a not so distant future. Furthermore, geopolitical shifts such as the return of the Trump administration in the United States would also influence the maritime dynamics in the Indo-Pacific. It is likely that a renewed trade war with China would escalate tensions in the South China Sea. In the Indian Ocean, the exploitation of

the deep seabed for mineral resources is projected to attract growing commercial interests with advancements in mining technology and increased demand civil and military demands for critical minerals.

Presently, various open source applications available in the public domain, such as the Global Fishing Watch³ provide unprecedented insights into global maritime fishing activities. However, these are just a glimpse of the potential, future technologies hold, considering the rapid pace at which maritime technology is evolving. Scientists and marine experts are already puzzled by recent discoveries of unknown species living deep in the oceans and baffled by phenomena such as black holes and oceanic sinkholes, which highlight the vast unknowns that still exist. As the ocean transparency improves and more is known about these unexplored frontiers, the discoveries would reshape not only the understanding of the ocean ecosystems but will have profound geopolitical and economic ramifications for the 21st century and beyond.

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³ Global Fishing Watch is an independent, international nonprofit organization. It was started by a website launched in September 2016 by Google in partnership with Oceana and SkyTruth to provide the world's first global view of commercial fishing activities. <https://globalfishingwatch.org/>

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GEOPOLITICA

ISSN 2009-9193
VOL XIV – N. 1/2025 – Gennaio-Giugno – January-June

CONFINE E FRONTIERA
IN GEOPOLITICA, NEL DIRITTO INTERNAZIONALE
E NELLE RELAZIONI INTERNAZIONALI

*BORDER AND FRONTIER
IN GEOPOLITICS, INTERNATIONAL LAW AND
INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS*

a cura di/edited by: Federico Bordonaro & Tiberio Graziani

ISBN: 9791281485211

Geopolitica – Registrazione presso il Tribunale di Roma
in data 21 dicembre 2011, n. 395/2011
Direttore responsabile: Tiberio Graziani